

EFFECTIVENESS OF A WEB BASED TEACHING PROGRAM DESIGNED ON MOODLE ON COVID-19 FOR B.SC. NURSING STUDENTS

*¹Fazl Ur Rahman and ²Sakshi Sood

^{1,2}Department of Medical Surgical, Nursing, Metro College of Health Science and Research, Gr. Noida (UP).

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*Corresponding Author: Fazl Ur Rahman

Department of Medical Surgical, Nursing, Metro college of Health Science and Research, Gr. Noida (UP).

Email Id: fazlwani2@gmail.com.

ASBTRACT

Introduction: The dynamic use of Internet facilities has shifted the teaching-learning process from traditional classroom teaching to the virtual learning environment. **Aim:** This quasi-experimental study was done to assess the effectiveness of a web-based teaching program designed on Moodle on “covid-19” for B. Sc. Nursing 4th year students. **Settings and Design:** Nonequivalent control group pretest posttest experimental design was used. A total of 90 nursing students were selected with total enumerative sampling from Metro college of Health Science and Research, Greater Noida (UP) and Kailash Institute of Nursing and Paramedical Science, Greater Noida (UP). **Subjects and Methods:** A structured knowledge questionnaire was used to assess the knowledge of students regarding covid-19. Group I, i.e., the experimental group received a web-based teaching program and Group II, i.e., control group received conventional teaching. Structured opinionnaire was used to assess the students’ acceptance toward web-based teaching program. **Results:** The post mean knowledge score of students in experimental group (24.80 and 23.83 on day 11 and 21) and conventional teaching program (24.4 and 24.1 on day 11 and 21) was higher than their pre intervention knowledge scores in Group I (15.89) and Group II (15.25). Thus, both web-based teaching program and conventional teaching were found equally effective at statistically significant at $P < 0.001$. More than half of the students (54.31%) strongly agreed that web-based teaching program design on Moodle regarding covid-19 was acceptable. **Conclusions:** Thus, both methods of teaching were found effective in proving education to students.

KEYWORDS: Conventional teaching and knowledge regarding covid-19, effectiveness, Moodle.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid progress in technology and the advancement in learning systems is embraced throughout the world. The introduction of computers was the basis of this revolution and with the passage of time, as we get hooked to smartphones, tablets, etc, these devices now have an importance in terms of learning. E-Learning or web-based education consist of teaching can be based in or out of the classrooms, the use of computers and the Internet. A learning system based on formalised teaching but with the help of electronic resources is known as web-based education or E-learning. While teaching can be based in or out of the classrooms, the use of computers and the Internet forms the major component of E-learning. E-learning can also be termed as a network enabled transfer of skills and knowledge, and the delivery of education is made to a large number of recipients at the same or different times. E-learning or web-based education is available to everyone, anywhere,

anytime irrespective of time and distance. Digital technologies are integrated more and more in our day-to-day life, and hence, it is also included in classroom practice. E-learning definition is defined as providing Training and development to the Students/Employees through various electronic media such as the internet, audio, video etc. Web-based learning or E-learning is also referred to as electronic learning or virtual learning.

Various Learning Management Systems have been used now a days, in which some are commercial software like Blackboard and WebCT, while others are open source softwares such as ATutor, Ilias, Moodle, and Claroline. Moodle (Modular Object Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment) is a course management system which enables delivery of web-based education. It helps in integration of various resources and assessment strategies and is good in content creation. It has been developed by Martin Dougiamas as a part of his PhD in

Education thesis. It helps in providing a wide range of resources for the students. It is an all-in-one learning platform with many features. It provides flexibility for the learners, as learners can access the study material from anywhere, like learners who lives at distance and does not have the interactions with the instructor. Although Moodle has been used in various other specialties like engineering etc., yet here has been limited research regarding use of Moodle in Nursing education. Thus, the researcher felt the need to conduct study in this region.

Review of literature

A large amount of research is available on the different types of e-learning technologies and infrastructures and how they contribute to education. Some research compares E-learning platforms while other research compares E-learning to the traditional face-to-face learning, or focuses on the design mode and application. The researched and recommended integration of Moodle with the existing LMSs to produce enhanced systems to accommodate the organisation's needs. The integrated design heavily involved the teachers and developers input. Even included the students input in the LMS integration for the Open University in UK. Implementation of Moodle to assist in the facilitation of E-learning was also supported by for the faculty of Maritime technology in the Szczecin University of Technology.

Medical education and training has been identifying as the aggressive users of E-learning and present a wide scope for induction of such practice in future. The study remarks that the scope, expectations and applicability for developing and developed courtesies differ significantly (Miklian, 2018).

A study based in Kingdom of Saudi Arabia by Intakhab A. Khan addresses the usefulness of e-learning in English education for Saudi students. It says that the involvement of the learners is an important aspect and e-learning through its innovative methods helps students relate to the techniques with ease. Resource generation, usefulness and effectiveness for students were some of the factors that were highlighted by the study as a mark of success of e-learning in English language for students in Saudi Arabia. The study has limitations of using only a specific country for the research base (Intakhab A. Khan, 2016).

Aim of the study

This quasi-experimental study was done to assess the effectiveness of a web-based teaching program designed on Moodle on "covid-19" for B. Sc. Nursing students.

Objectives of the study

1) To compare the pretest and posttest knowledge scores of B. Sc. nursing 4th year students related to covid-19 after administration of web-based teaching program

- 2) To compare the posttest knowledge scores of B. Sc. Nursing 4th year students related to covid-19 between experimental and control group
- 3) To assess the acceptability of web-based teaching program on covid-19 designed on Moodle

Methodology

Quantitative quasi-experimental research approach and nonequivalent control group pretest posttest control group design was used in the study.

- Population: B. Sc. Nursing students
- Sample: B. Sc. Nursing 4th year students of Metro college of Health Science and Research, Greater Noida (UP) and Kailash Institute of Nursing and Paramedical Science, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh (UP)
- Sample: 95(Group I [55] and Group II [40])
- Sampling Technique: Total enumerative sampling technique
- Null Hypotheses-All the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of statistical significance
- HO1 = There will be no significant difference in the mean pretest and posttest knowledge scores of B. Sc. Nursing students using web-based teaching program on covid-19
- HO2 = There will be no significant difference in the mean pretest and posttest knowledge scores of B. Sc. nursing students in the control group receiving conventional method of teaching.
- HO3 = There will be no significant difference in the mean posttest knowledge scores of B. Sc. Nursing students using web-based teaching program and control group.

Variables of the study

Dependent variable

Knowledge of B. Sc. Nursing 4th year students regarding covid-19.

Independent variables

Web-based teaching program designed on Moodle for B. Sc. Nursing 4th year students regarding covid-19 and conventional teaching regarding covid-19.

Data collection tool and techniques based on objectives of the study, following tools were prepared:

- Tool I: Structured knowledge questionnaire (KR20 = 0.84). The structured questionnaire consists of two sections, section A consists of 10 demographic questions, while section B consists of 50 MCQs related to covid-19 which carries 1 mark each. The maximum score was 50, while the minimum score was 0
- Tool II: Structured opinionnaire (Cronbach alpha, $r = 0.73$). There are three point rating scale containing eight statements related to web-based teaching program designed on Moodle regarding covid-19.

Validity

The content validity of tools was done by a panel of five experts from medical and nursing field, who had expertise in developing such instruments and the necessary modification was done accordingly.

Ethical clearance

Ethical permission was obtained from the administrative authorities of Metro college of Health Science and Research, Greater Noida (UP) and Kailash Institute of Nursing and Paramedical Science, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh (UP).

Data collection procedure

The study was conducted in the Metro college of Health Science and Research, Greater Noida (UP) and Kailash Institute of Nursing and Paramedical Science, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh (UP) during the month of April 2021 after getting ethical clearance from the administrative authorities.

- Day 1-Pre-test was conducted on both the Group I and Group II using structured knowledge questionnaire
- Day 1-10-Interventions were given to both the groups, web-based teaching program designed on Moodle regarding covid-19 to Group I and conventional teaching regarding covid-19 to Group II
- Day 11-Post-test I was conducted from both the Group I and Group II
- Day 21-Post-test II was conducted from both the groups using structured knowledge questionnaire.

Structured opinionnaire was administered to the Group I to assess the acceptability of the web-based teaching program designed on Moodle regarding covid-19.

Description of intervention

Training program on COVID-19

The training program on covid-19 was prepared for B. Sc. Nursing 4th students by the researcher. Five modules were developed related to covid-19, with illustrations. Power point shows were developed. Content validation of the training program was done by experts.

The total duration of program was 10 h, 1 h each day for 10 days. For first 2 days emphasis was given on

introduction and classification about covid-19. Day 3–4 focused on symptoms of covid-19. On day 5–6, emphasis was given on covid-19 spread. Day 7–8, emphasized on medication and focus was prevention of covid-19 on day 9–10. Accounts were made on Moodle and Log in Ids and passwords were given to students in the Group I to access the training program on covid-19.

Conventional teaching was given to Group II regarding covid-19 for 10 days. Regular follow-ups were made to answer the questions and clear the doubts of the students.

Online teaching learning activities were used for Group I and lecture and discussion were used for Group II.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the mean age of students in experimental group is 20.60 and in control group 20.65, and hence, there is no significant difference among the mean age of both groups. Hence, both the groups were homogeneous with respect to age.

Table 2 shows that there was no significant difference among the students in Group I and Group II with respect to demographic variable such as attended any online web-based teaching program (0.785), attended any online course on covid-19 (0.071), attended any workshop or conference on covid-19 (0.694), previous year marks of students (0.837), area of stay (0.564), and schooling (0.295), while there was a significant difference in the gender (0.001) and educational status of parents (0.000). Thus, adjusted analysis was performed keeping these variables as covariate.

Table 3 shows that the mean pretest knowledge score of experimental group is 15.89, while the mean pretest knowledge score of the control group is 15.25, $P = 0.197$. Thus, there is no significant difference among the knowledge of students regarding covid-19 during pretest. Thus, the groups were homogeneous with respect to pre-test knowledge scores.

Table 4 shows there is significant difference among the mean knowledge scores of students regarding covid-19 in pretest (15.89) and posttest (24.80 and 23.83) in the experimental group. Thus, the null hypothesis H_0 is rejected. This indicates that web-based teaching program is effective in improving students' knowledge.

Table 1: "T-test" computed to compare distribution of age of B.Sc. Nursing 4th year students between experimental and control group $n=(n_1+n_2)=95$.

Variable	Mean±SD		Test applied	Test value	df	p
	Experimental group (n1=55)	Control group (n2=40)				
Age(years)	20.60±0.93	20.65±1.21	Independent t- test	-0.113	93	0.487

SD: Standard deviation, Df: Degrees of freedom

Table 2: Demographic profile of B.Sc. Nursing 4th year students in experimental and control group n= (n1+n2)=95.

Variable	Categories	Frequency (%)		Test applied	Test value	df	p
		Experimental group (n1=55), n (%)	Control group (n2=40), n (%)				
Gender	Male Female	20 (36.4) 35 (63.6)	28 (70.0) 12 (30.0)	χ^2	10.482	1	0.001***
Online/web-based teaching course	Yes No	10 (18.2) 45 (81.8)	6 (15.0) 34 (85.0)	χ^2	0.167	1	0.785
Online course on covid-19	Yes No	0 (0) 55 (100.0)	3 (7.5) 37 (92.5)	Fisher exact test	4.26	1	0.071
Workshop/conference on covid-19	Yes No	3 (5.5) 52 (94.5)	3 (7.5) 37 (92.5)	Fisher exact test	0.164	1	0.694
Percentage of marks in previous year examination	>75% 50-75%	29 (52.7) 26 (47.3)	20 (50.0) 20 (50.0)	χ^2	0.069	1	0.837
Education status of father	No formal education Primary education Secondary education Degree/diploma Postgraduation or higher	1 (1.8) 2 (3.6) 16 (29.1) 26 (47.3) 10 (18.2)	1 (2.5) 5 (12.5) 28 (70.0) 5 (12.5) 1 (2.5)	Fisher exact test	24.387	4	0.000***
Education status of mother	No formal education Primary education Secondary education Degree/diploma Postgraduation or higher	5 (9.1) 2 (3.6) 35 (63.6) 10 (18.2) 3 (5.5)	10 (25.0) 14 (35.0) 15 (37.5) 1 (2.5) 0 (0)	Fisher exact test	27.344	4	0.000***
Area of stay	Hostel Home Any another	31 (56.4) 15 (27.3) 9 (16.4)	22 (55.0) 14 (35.0) 4 (10.0)	χ^2	1.146	2	0.564
Schooling	Private Public	48 (87.3) 7 (12.7)	38 (95.0) 2 (5.0)	χ^2	1.612	1	0.295

***Significant, p <0.001 level. Df: Degrees of freedom

Table 3: "T-test" computed to compare pretest knowledge scores of adolescents related to covid-19 between the experimental and control group (n=95).

Group	Mean±SD	t	p
Experimental (n1=55)	15.89±3.96	0.717	0.197
Control (n2=40)	15.25±4.72		

SD: Standard deviation

There was also a significant difference among the mean knowledge scores of students regarding covid-19 in pretest (15.25) and posttest (24.4 and 24.1) in the control group. Thus, the null hypothesis HO2 is rejected. This indicates that conventional teaching is also effective in improving students' knowledge Table 5 shows, there is significant difference between the mean knowledge scores of pretest and first posttest, and pretest and second posttest while there is no significant difference between the mean knowledge scores of first posttest and second posttest in both the Group I and Group II, thus both web-based teaching program designed on Moodle and conventional teaching were significantly effective and the students were able to retain the knowledge gained from both web-based teaching and conventional

teaching. Table 6 shows that there is no significant difference among the knowledge of students regarding covid-19 in posttest 1 and posttest 2 of both the experimental group and control group, i.e., P = 0.586 for posttest 1 and P = 0.462 for posttest 2.

Table 4: Repeated measures ANOVA computed to compare pre- and post-test knowledge scores of B.Sc. Nursing 4th year students related to covid-19 in experimental and control group (n=95).

Groups	Mean±SD			df	F	p
	Pretest (day 1)	Posttest (day 11)	Posttest (day 21)			
Experimental group (n1=55)	15.89±3.96	24.80±5.05	23.83±5.73	2.00	50.928	0.000***
Control group (n2=40)	15.25±4.72	24.4±5.42	24.1±5.26	2.00	76.523	0.000***

***Significant at 0.001 level. SD: Standard deviation, Df: Degrees of freedom

Table 5: Pairwise comparisons for pre-test and post-test knowledge scores of B.Sc. Nursing 4th year students related to covid-19 in experimental group and control group (n=95).

Group	Time points	Mean difference	P	95% CI for difference	
				Lower bound	Upper bound
Experimental group	1-2	-8.909	0.000***	-6.694	-11.124
	2-3	0.964	0.605	2.805	-0.878
	3-1	7.945	0.000***	10.293	5.598
Control group	1-2	-9.250	0.000***	-7.395	-11.105
	-3	0.400	0.630	1.185	-0.385
	3-1	8.850	0.000***	10.717	6.983

***Significant at .001 level. CI: Confidence interval

Table 6: "T-test" computed to compare post-test knowledge scores of students related to covid-19 between the experimental and control group (n=95).

Time points	Group	Mean±SD	t	p
Posttest 1 (Day 11)	Experimental (n=55)	24.80±5.05	0.277	0.586
	Control(n=40)	24.50±5.42		
Posttest 2 (Day 21)	Experimental (n=55)	23.83±5.73	-0.229	0.462
	Control (n=40)	24.10±5.26		

SD: Standard deviation

Hence, the null hypothesis HO3 is accepted. Hence, it shows that there is no significant difference between the knowledge scores of the students using web-based teaching program or conventional teaching. The data represented in Table 7 shows that according to the opinion of the students, web based teaching program designed on Moodle is acceptable (54.31%).

DISCUSSION

The current study shows that both the teaching methods, i.e., web-based teaching program and traditional teaching where there is face-to-face teacher student interaction, are equally effective in providing education to students. Similar findings have been reported by many researchers.

A similar study was conducted to compare online and classroom-based formats for teaching emergency medicine to medical students, the results of the study showed no significant difference in the knowledge gain between online and classroom-based teaching groups, suggesting that both methods of instruction provide equivalent learning by Swaminatha V. Mahadevan. Although initially, it is difficult to convince students and faculty about online teaching, but once it is started they begin to enjoy. High-level technology like bandwidth, uninterrupted Internet supply is key essential things

which are needed to make it successful. Students exposed to Moodle software expressed that online method of teaching was interesting, motivating and user friendly. The use of online technology must be encouraged among students and faculty members for academic purposes.

CONCLUSIONS

Web-based teaching and traditional teaching, both are effective in improving knowledge of students, web-based teaching program designed on Moodle is accepted by the students. Similar kind of study can be conducted for a larger group with different specialties at different settings.

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Table 7: Frequency and percentage distribution of the opinion of B.Sc. Nursing 4th year students on web-based teaching program (n=55).

Serial number	Responses	Frequency (%)		
		Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree
1	The content is understandable	33 (60.0)	21 (38.2)	1 (1.8)
2	The content is according to the syllabus	34 (61.8)	18 (32.7)	3 (5.5)
3	The content is interesting to read	25 (45.5)	27 (49.1)	3 (5.5)
4	Language is clear and simple	30 (54.5)	23 (41.8)	2 (3.6)
5	The content is motivating to read	24 (43.6)	31 (56.4)	0
6	The content is appropriate in response to the time period provided to read	26 (47.3)	26 (47.3)	3 (5.5)
7	It is easy to use online teaching method	34 (61.8)	21 (38.2)	0
8	Web-based teaching program is more interesting than traditional teaching	33 (60.0)	22 (40.0)	0
Overall percentage		54.31	42.95	2.72

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